

GAME-BASED LEARNING TOWARDS STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION

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Game-Based Learning Towards Students' Performance in Technology and Livelihood Education

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the impact of game-based learning on the learning outcomes and performance of Grade 8 Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) students at Cabibihan National High School. The pre-experimental method was employed with a sample of thirty-two (32) students from Cabibihan National High School, Tagkawayan District I, Division of Quezon. Data were collected using a survey and an adapted questionnaire instrument. In this study, the researcher gathered data of the respondents in terms of their profile, perception on game-based learning materials and pre-test and post-test scores in beauty care (nail care services). The findings revealed that students strongly agreed with the functionality, accessibility, and technicality of the game-based learning approach. The students perceived their learning outcomes as observed after using game-based learning in terms of the use of nail care tools and equipment, maintaining tools and equipment, practicing occupational health and safety procedures, and practicing basic nail design. The study found a significant relationship between game-based learning and all the learning outcomes measured by the design instrument. However, there was no significant relationship between the game-based learning application and the student's second-quarter performance.

Keywords: *game-based learning, technology, livelihood education*

Introduction

In the changing world of education, it has become crucial to incorporate technology and innovative teaching methods to create a dynamic and engaging learning environment. Traditional teaching techniques often need help to capture the attention and interest of today's digital-native students, especially in subjects like technology and livelihood education (TLE). Technology and Livelihood Education, commonly known as TLE, plays a role in our education system. Its purpose is to provide students with skills and knowledge directly applicable to their future careers and daily lives. TLE encompasses a wide array of subjects, including but not limited to computer science, agriculture, culinary arts, and entrepreneurship. Given its practical nature, TLE demands an interactive and immersive approach to education that can effectively bridge the gap between theory and application.

Education, also referred to as TLE (Technical and Livelihood Education), is a crucial component of our education system. The primary objective of this program is to provide students with practical skills and knowledge that may be directly applied to their future professional endeavors and everyday activities. TLE covers a broad range of courses, such as computer science, agriculture, culinary arts, and entrepreneurship. Due to its pragmatic characteristics, TLE necessitates an engaging and immersive educational strategy that can effectively connect theoretical knowledge with practical application. The objective of this study is to assess the efficacy of game-based educational resources on the academic performance and learning outcomes of eighth-grade students.

The landscape of education has been evolving rapidly in response to the dynamic needs and preferences of today's learners. Traditional pedagogical approaches have been used in the educational system for a long time; while they are effective, they don't involve active participation from the students, which makes lessons difficult to understand, especially in areas that call for practical applications and the development of skills. Innovative teaching techniques have become crucial tools for educators to bridge the gap between conventional approaches and the expectations of students who were raised in a digital age. This is because education is increasingly integrating technology into the learning process.

In line with the growing problems in teaching strategies and as a lot of pedagogical methods are increasingly being challenged by the need to adapt to the changing needs and preferences of students, researchers are exerting efforts to look for the strategies which will bridge this gap. Thus, a lot of innovative strategies had emerged especially in time of the pandemic. One of the strategies emerged in the digital period is the game-based learning.

Games have the potential to simulate real-world scenarios, provide immediate feedback, and foster a sense of competition and achievement, all of which can enhance the learning experience. The use of games to encourage student learning in the past was appealed to attract students' attention with the rationale of "we all learn better when motivated" (Bergin and Reilly 2005). On the other hand, the use of game-based learning techniques eliminates the formality of learning and enables students to study while having fun. By incorporating aspects typically found in games, such as challenges, prizes, competition, and narrative-driven scenarios, it turns learning into a fun and participatory experience. Integrating innovative approaches, such as game-based learning, may hold the key to improving student engagement and knowledge retention. Game-based learning is an approach that leverages the principles of gamification to engage students in a learning process that is both enjoyable and educational. It plays a pivotal role in equipping students with practical skills and knowledge for future career opportunities and everyday life specially in an exploratory courses like Technology and Livelihood Education.

Technology and Livelihood Education is a subject area where practical skills and hands-on learning play a pivotal role. TLE encompasses diverse subjects, including but not limited to information and communication technology, entrepreneurship, home economics, and industrial arts. This subject area is unique in its emphasis on hands-on learning, problem-solving, and real-world application of knowledge. Thus, Game-based learning offers an interactive and immersive experience that encourages active participation and problem-solving, making it a particularly promising approach for TLE, which often involves practical applications and skill development.

Incorporating game-based learning materials into TLE curricula has the potential to address some of the challenges faced by educators and students in this field. Moreover, practical subjects often require students to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts, which can be challenging to achieve through traditional teaching methods alone. Additionally, game-based learning can provide instant feedback, promote problem-solving, and encourage students to explore and experiment.

Despite the potential benefits of game-based learning, there is a gap in the existing research literature regarding its effectiveness in improving the performance and learning outcomes of Grade 8 students in Technology and Livelihood Education (Beauty Care Nail care services). While studies have explored game-based learning in various educational contexts, the specific impact on TLE at this grade level remains underexplored. Additionally, most studies in this field have provided limited insights into the specific impact of game-based learning materials on Grade 8 students' performance and learning outcomes in TLE. Thus, it is imperative to investigate whether game-based learning materials can indeed bridge the existing gap in student engagement and learning outcomes in TLE. Therefore, it is essential to investigate how game-based learning materials can enhance the learning experiences of Grade 8 students in TLE, addressing the gap in existing research.

This research aimed to contribute to the field of education by providing empirical evidence and insights into the impact of game-based learning materials on Grade 8 students' performance and learning outcomes in Technology and Livelihood Education.

The findings of this study have the potential to inform educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers about the effectiveness of game-based learning in practical subjects like TLE. Additionally, the study may identify challenges and barriers to implementation, offering recommendations and best practices for optimizing the integration of game-based learning materials into Grade 8 TLE curricula.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the Effectiveness of Game-based learning on Students' learning outcomes in Beauty Care Nail care Services at Cabibihan National High School. The following questions were addressed in this study:

1. What is the Profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. previous grades in first quarter;
 - 1.4. parents education; and
 - 1.5. family income?
2. To what extent do students-respondents perceive the use of the game-based learning in terms of:
 - 2.1. functionality;
 - 2.2. accessibility; and
 - 2.3. technicality?
3. What are the Pre Test and Post Test Scores of the respondents in Beauty Care Nail Care Services in terms of:
 - 3.1. use of nail care tools and equipment;
 - 3.2. maintain tools and equipment;
 - 3.3. practice occupational health and safety procedures; and
 - 3.4. practice basic nail design?
4. What is the level of respondent's performance in beauty care (Nail care services) after exposure to game-based learning?
5. Is there significant difference between the pre-test and post test scores of the students-respondents before and after using game-based learning
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' perception on game-based learning and their performance in Beauty Care?

Literature Review

Game-based learning employs game aspects, game thinking, and game mechanics in non-game situations to captivate participants in an activity (Tu et al., 2014). Games facilitate the combination of inherent and external incentive elements to create an atmosphere where players are more inclined to participate in the desired activities.

In a nutrition course, Yien, Hung, Hwang, and Lin (2011) employed game-based learning and found that this method improved student attitudes and learning effectiveness more than typical PowerPoint teaching and even had an impact on their eating habits. The

instructional technique must be suitable for the type of knowledge and the desired learning objectives, just like any other teaching strategy. The relationship between learning levels (knowledge), potential instructional methodologies to meet those learning objectives, and different game types that could be utilized to assist the learning outcomes is illustrated by Kapp (2012) in his book *The Gamification of Learning and Instruction*. For instance, according to Kapp (2012), in order to acquire problem-solving skills, a student must face unfamiliar circumstances and use prior knowledge to find solutions. It is possible to teach this by providing numerous instances of various kinds of related difficulties. It is advised to play games that highlight various settings and circumstances, such as quest games and resource allocation. Its effectiveness will be maximized if the instructional technique and game elements are designed to match the targeted learning objectives and the level of learning.

Game-based learning is the use of game elements, game thinking, and game mechanics in non-game contexts to engage users in an activity (Tu et al., 2014). Games enable the integration of both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational components to cultivate an environment where players feel more motivated to engage in the target activities. For example, in a video game such as *The Sims*, the player is in full control of what happens in the game (autonomy) or in games similar to *Farmville* the players experience a lot of social interactions with other players (relatedness). Eseryel et al. (2014), also found in their study that social interactivity during gameplay (collaboration and competition with others) contributes significantly to student engagement.

In the study conducted by Ronimus et al. (2014) they recommended game design elements being added in addition to instructional support for students in future studies to determine whether the increase in engagement that initially occurs when digital game-based learning is used can last over an extended period.

Stimulated by the effects that game elements can produce, many researchers have looked into the influence of gamification in an educational context, getting favorable results, such as the increase of engagement, user retention, knowledge, and cooperation (Hakulinen & Auvinen 2014; Tvarozek & Brza 2014). Despite that, some studies have shown uncertain or prejudicial results from gamification (Christy and Fox 2014). Lee and Hao (2015) and Woo (2014) found that digital game-based learning to have a positive or significant impact on student motivation.

Game design should be a progressive exercise (Tu et al., 2014). Game-based learning is a cyclical, iterative process that includes motivation, action and feedback. According to research by Giannakas et al. (2017), teachers may not be able to provide enough support for students, especially those who struggle academically, if there are no instructional frameworks available to go along with mobile game-based learning. According to (Khan et al., 2017, p. 2773), one method an instructional framework may be used to support students and build a connection to curriculum areas is by integrating GBL ID when designing lessons that incorporate digital game-based learning. "While actively involved in a game, our brains experience the joy of struggling with, and coming to understand, new systems, concepts, and perspectives. The same principles apply to digital games" (Jukes, 2017).

According to (Harlt et al., 2020), The kind of games that should be used in schools is determined by the subject matter, its content, and the judgment of teachers. A teacher may decide to implement modular game-based exercises and a hybrid approach to counteract the detrimental effects of extrinsic incentives using a comprehensive strategy. Since a hybrid method offers a smooth transition with a manageable balance of novelty and familiarity, it might also be a more practical means of bringing new pedagogical tools to higher education learning acquaintanceship. There was an increase in student motivation in a game-based learning environment.

Methodology

Respondents

Purposive sampling technique was applied in this study since only students from one section would be the respondents of the study which was composed of 32 heterogeneous learners from the chosen section handled by the researcher.

Instruments

The researcher gathered relevant data for this study, the researcher utilized various techniques which were validated by the experts in the field. The following instruments were used to enhance the performance in Beauty care nail care services of the respondents.

Survey questionnaire was used to identify the students perception in the Game-based learning instruction of the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire composed of the profile of the respondents, five statements/questions in learner perception on the game-based learning. Lastly consists of the First quarter grade of the students.

The second instrument was the validated pretest and post test in Written works and performance in Nail care services. It was composed of ten questions per variable.

The Third instrument would be the rubric. This was the measuring tool that the research used to assess learners' skills performance. This rubric was adopted on the K To 12 learning Module in Beauty Care nail care services.

Procedure

In gathering the data needed, the researchers coordinated and ask permission from the principal of Cabibihan National High School to

conduct the research.

After approval, the researcher administered the pretest during class hours to determine their academic learning performance. Afterward, the respondents were given the Game-Based Learning approach, which clearly defined the learning outcomes they wanted to achieve. The researcher makes a lesson exemplar that contains the lesson proper from activity, analysis, abstraction and application. Using game-based learning, the teacher chooses games that align with the learning objectives and are suitable for the age and interests of students. After that the researcher evaluates the student learning through a variety of assessments using the game-based learning materials that determine the key concepts or skills that the teacher want students to grasp through the game-based learning experience then the researcher was give post-test to the respondents this is to determine if there was significant difference between academic performance of the respondents through the result of Pre-Test and Post-Test.

Ethical Considerations

Before the conduct of the study, the respondents were assured that the information acquired from them would be utilized just for research purposes and would not be reflected in their real class performance. The respondents were told that the information gathered from them would only be used for research purposes and would not be reflected in their actual class performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered through the research instruments provided which are presented in tabular form and statistically evaluated to address study's problem.

Profile of the Conversational Partners

Part I- Profile of the Respondents

This part presents data on the frequency and percentage distribution of the profiles of the respondents of TLE Grade 8 students at Cabibihan National High School. This includes age, sex, a parent's occupation, and family income.

Table 1 reveals that the majority of the Grade 8 students respondents at Cabibihan National High School are 13 years old, with 53.125 percent, followed by 14 years old with 34.375 percent, and 12.5 percent with the age of 15. This result shows that the students in Grade 8 are mostly 13 to 14 years old.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Age

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
13	17	53.125
14	11	34.375
15	4	12.5
Total	32	100

Table 2 reveals that both males and females have a high frequency of Grade 8 students at Cabibihan National High School. The total number of respondents is 32; both are 50 percent. This result shows that the population of respondents has the same number.

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents in Terms of Sex

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	16	50
Female	16	50
Total	32	100

Table 3 shows that most previous grades in Technology and Livelihood Education of grade 8 students respondents in Cabibihan National High Schools is 95 with 2 or 6.25 %, followed by 90-94 with 12 or 37.5 %, followed by 85-89 with 15 or 46.8 % Meanwhile 80-84 with 3 or 9.3 % for the 75-79 got 0 %

Table 3. Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Previous grades in TLE 8

<i>Previous Grade</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
95-above	2	6.25
90-94	12	37.5
85-89	15	46.875
80-84	3	9.375
75-79	0	0
Total	32	100

Table 4 revealed that most of the respondent's father's education was elementary, consisting of 18 or 56.25 percent, 8 or 25 percent with secondary education, and 6 or 18.75 percent with college or tertiary education. It shows that most Grade 8 students have fathers

with elementary education. It also revealed that most of the respondent's education in their mother was elementary, with 16 or 50 percent, followed by 14 or 43.75 percent in secondary and 2 or 6.25 percent in college or tertiary. It was revealed that the majority of the respondent's parents's educational attainment was elementary school.

Table 4. *Distribution of Respondents in terms of Parent's Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Father		Mother	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	18	56.25	16	50
Secondary	8	25	14	43.75
College/Tertiary	6	18.75	2	6.25
Total	32	100	32	100

In terms of family income, Table 5 reveals that most respondents have 10,000 below with 20 or 62.5 percent, followed by 10,001 to 20,000 with 10 or 31.25 percent; however, respondents with 20,001 to 30,000 and 30,000 to 50,000 have the same frequency with 1 or 3.125 percent, while respondents with 50,000 and above income have 0 frequency and 0 percentage. It shows that the family income of the student respondents was mostly below 10,000.

Table 5. *Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Family's Income*

Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below 10,001	20	62.5
10,001 – 20,000	10	31.25
20,001 – 30,000	1	3.125
30,001 – 50,000	1	3.125
50,001 and Above	0	0
Total	32	100

The second part of the discussion was all about the learners' perception on Game-based learning. This consist of three table and a summary table for all indicators.

Table 6. *Perception on Game Based learning in TLE 8 in terms of Functionality*

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Increase the retention level of the students performance	4.68	.470	Strongly Agree
2. Help the student's easily understand the lesson.	4.68	.470	Strongly Agree
3. Help students to improve their creativity, critical and problem solving skills.	4.59	.498	Strongly Agree
4. Enhance ability to retain the concept of the lesson.	4.68	.470	Strongly Agree
5. Help the students to enjoy and encourage the desire to explore and discover new things.	4.78	.420	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.68	0.466	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1-1.49 Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49- Disagree 2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree 3.50-4.49- Agree 4.50- 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table portrays the student's perception of game-based learning in terms of its functionality. The indicator "Help the students to enjoy and encourage the desire to explore and discover new things" has the highest mean of 4.78 with the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." The lowest mean is 4.59 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" The indicator "helps students to improve their creativity, critical and problem solving skills." The overall mean of students' perception on Game-Based learning in terms of delivery of functionality is 4.68, with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree."

According to Matic et al. (2023), games incorporate elements like points, badges, leather boards and storylines, making learning feel more like play. This intrinsic motivation can lead to a more enjoyable learning experience. Games provide a dynamic and interactive environment where students can actively participate in learning. The interactivity is often more engaging than traditional passive learning methods.

In addition, well-designed educational games often have open-ended environments or challenges that encourage students to explore different strategies and solutions. This fosters a sense of discovery and experimentation. Usually, games provide immediate feedback on students actions allowing them to learn from mistakes and refine their approaches. This iterative process encourages exploration and a willingness to try new things. With this, games can spark curiosity by presenting students with novel situations and challenges. This curiosity can motivate them to explore further and delve deeper into the subject matter.

Table 7 portrays the student's perception of Game based learning in terms of the Accessibility The indicator "The Game-Based learning provides sufficient support student's learning" has the highest mean of 4.84 with the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." the indicator "Students navigate the interactive game easily."has the lowest mean is 4.59 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" The overall mean of students' perception of game based learning in terms of Accessibility is 4.70, with a verbal interpretation of

"Strongly Agree" De Vero and Barr (2023), games can make learning more interactive and enjoyable, leading to higher student engagement and learning motivation.

Table 7. Perception on Game Based learning in TLE 8 in terms of Accessibility

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. Students navigate the interactive game easily	4.59	.559	Strongly Agree
2. Game-Based learning through interactive games provide clear instructions.	4.68	.470	Strongly Agree
3. Provide Opportunities for collaboration among students.	4.75	.508	Strongly Agree
4. Game-Based Learning is convenient is convenient to students with different learning styles.	4.65	.545	Strongly Agree
5. Game-Based learning provides sufficient support student's learning.	4.84	.368	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.706	0.490	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1-1.49 Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49- Disagree 2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree 3.50-4.49- Agree 4.50- 5.00 Strongly Agree

The repetitive nature of gameplay can help students solidify their knowledge and improve their ability to recall information. In addition, multiplayer games can encourage teamwork, Communication and collaboration skills. Adaptive game-based learning platforms can tailor the difficulty and content to individual student needs. However it is important to note that games should be aligned with the curriculum and complement other learning activities. Assessing student learning outcomes after playing educational games is crucial to measure their effectiveness. Overall, game-based learning can provide sufficient support for student learning when implemented effectively.

Table 8. Perception on Game Based learning in TLE 8 in terms of Technicality

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
1. The set of rules is easy to understand	4.78	.420	Strongly Agree
2. The game-Based learning has essential technical features.	4.56	.564	Strongly Agree
3. Technical aspect is easily to use	4.65	.545	Strongly Agree
4. Using Game- Based is comprehensive and effortless.	4.71	.522	Strongly Agree
5. Technical aspect of game-based learning can easily change based on the needs of the students.	4.62	.553	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.66	0.521	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1-1.49 Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49- Disagree 2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree 3.50-4.49- Agree 4.50- 5.00 Strongly Agree

Table portrays the student's perception of Game based learning in terms of the Technicality The indicator " The set of rules is easy to understand" has the highest mean of 4.78 with the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." The game-Based learning has essential technical features." the lowest mean is 4.56 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" The overall mean of students' perception of game-based learning in terms of Technicality is 4.66, with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" activities in digital game-based learning can vary from solving basic puzzles to honing complex problem-solving techniques. Digital game-based learning involves activities that can range from completing very simple tasks to the development of intricate problem-solving skills. According to Patricia Deubel, games can be categorized as "action, adventure, fighting, puzzle, role-playing, sports, and strategy."

Table 9. Summary Table on Game-Based learning

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Functionality	4.68	0.46	Strongly Agree
Accessibility	4.70	0.49	Strongly Agree
Technicality	4.66	0.52	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.68	0.49	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1-1.49 Strongly Disagree 1.50-2.49- Disagree 2.50-3.49- Moderately Agree 3.50-4.49- Agree 4.50- 5.00 Strongly Agree

The Table shows the summary of game-based learning; this table reveals that the indicator "accessibility" gets the highest mean of 4.70 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." The indicator "functionality" gets the second highest mean of 4.68 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." It is followed by the indicator "technicality," which gets a mean of 4.66 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." The perception of the students on game-based learning gets an overall mean of 4.68 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree."

Learning should not be viewed as boring, and it does not imply that students should memorize concepts with comprehension by padding or repetition (Lameras et al., 2017). According to Alfarsi, Jasiya, Ragad, Abir, and Maryam, 2019; Tawafak, 2019; Tawafak, Romli, Ruzaini, & Sohail, 2019; Mathew, Malik, & Tawafak, 2019). The purpose of using games in the classroom is to get pupils interested in learning and to help them retain the material. While memorization is not the same as learning, students can utilize the game to help them retain key information for exams and real-world applications.

Table 10 shows the TLE Grade 8 students' pre-test in beauty care before exposing them to the game-based learning on the use of nail care tools and equipment. According to the categorization above in terms of Use of nail care tools and equipment it can be noted that

both scores of 0-2 and 3-4 got the same frequency of 10 or 31.25 percent got the remark of “Poor” and “fair” followed by the scores of 5-6 with a frequency of 7 or 21.875 percent got the remark of “Good” Meanwhile 5 or 15.625 percent of the students got the scores of 7-8 with a remarks of “Very good” The results showed that the pre-test of the grade 8 students have a poor and fair understanding in terms of the Use of nail care tools and equipment.

Table 10. Pre-test score of the respondents in beauty care (nail care services)

SCORES	Use of Nail Care tools and equipment		Maintain tools and equipment		Practice occupational health and safety procedures		Practice basic nail design		Remarks
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	frequency	Percentage	
9-10	-	-	-	-	-	-	21	65.625	Excellent
7-8	5	15.625	-	-	-	-	7	21.875	Very Good
5-6	7	21.875	7	21.875	8	25	3	9.375	Good
3-4	10	31.25	14	43.75	12	37.5	1	3.125	Fair
0-2	10	31.25	11	34.375	12	37.5	-	-	Poor
Total	32	100	32	100	32	100	32	100	

Legend: 0-2-Poor 3-4-Fair 5-6- Good 7-8- Very Good 9-10- Excellent

In terms of Maintaining tools and equipment it can be noted that the scores 3-4 got the highest frequency of 14 or 43.75 percent with a remarks of “Fair” followed by the scores of 0-2 with a frequency of 11 or 34.375 percent with a remarks of “Poor” Lastly the scores of 5-6 got the frequency of 7 with a percent of 21.875 percent with a remarks of “Good”. The results showed that the pre-test of the grade 8 students in terms of maintaining tools and equipment have “fair” understanding.

In terms of Occupational health and safety procedures both scores of 0-2 and 3-4 got the same frequency of 12 or 37.5 percent with a remarks of “fair” and “poor” Meanwhile the score of 5-6 got the frequency of 8 or 25 percent with a remarks of “good” The results showed that the pre-test of the grade 8 students have a poor and fair understanding in terms of the Occupational health and safety procedures.

In terms of Practice basic nail design the scores of 3-4 got the frequency of 1 or 3.125 percent with a remarks of “fair” while the scores of 5-6 got the frequency of 3 or 9.375 percent with a remarks of “good” the 7-8 scores got the frequency of 7 or 21.875 percent with a remarks of “very good” Lastly the scores of 9-10 got the frequency of 21 or 65.625 percent with a remarks of “excellent” The results showed that the pre-test of the grade 8 students have a excellent understanding in terms of the Practice basic nail design.

Table 12. Post-test score of the respondents in beauty care (nail care services)

SCORES	Use of Nail Care tools and equipment		Maintain tools and equipment		Practice occupational health and safety procedures		Practice basic nail design		Remarks
	F	P	F	%	F	%	F	%	
9-10	23	71.875	5	15.625	21	65.625	30	93.75	Excellent
7-8	6	18.75	11	34.375	7	21.875	2	6.25	Very Good
5-6	3	9.375	11	34.375	3	9.375	-	-	Good
3-4	-	-	5	15.625	1	3.125	-	-	Fair
0-2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Poor
Total	32	100	32	100	32	100	32	100	

Legend: 0-2-Poor 3-4-Fair 5-6- Good 7-8- Very Good 9-10- Excellent

Table 12 shows the TLE Grade 8 students' post-test in beauty care after exposing them to the game-based learning on the use of nail care tools and equipment. According to the categorization above in terms of Use of nail care tools and equipment it can be noted that the scores of 5-6 with a frequency of 3 or 9.375 percent got the remark of “Good” Meanwhile 6 or 18.75 percent of the students got the scores of 7-8 with a remarks of “Very good” Lastly the highest frequency of 23 or 71.875 got the score of 9-10 with a remarks of “Excellent” The results showed that the post-test of the grade 8 students have an “Excellent” understanding in terms of the Use of nail care tools and equipment.

In terms of Maintaining tools and equipment it can be noted that the scores 3-4 got the highest frequency of 5 or 15.625 percent with a remarks of “Fair” followed by the both scores of 5-6 and 7-8 with a frequency of 11 or 34.375 percent with a remarks of “Very good” and “good” Lastly the scores of 9-10 got the frequency of 5 with a percent of 15.625 percent with a remarks of “Excellent”. The results showed that the post -test of the grade 8 students in terms of maintaining tools and equipment have “Good” and “Very good” understanding.

In terms of Occupational health and safety procedures the scores of 3-4 got the frequency of 1 or 3.125 percent with a remarks of “fair”. Meanwhile the score of 5-6 got the frequency of 3 or 9.375 percent with a remarks of “good” the scores of 7-8 got the frequency of 7 or 21.875 percent with a remarks of “Ver good “ Lastly the scores 9-10 got the frequency of 21 or 65.625 percent with a remarks of “Excellent” The results showed that the post-test of the grade 8 students have an Excellent understanding in terms of the Occupational health and safety procedures.

In terms of Practice basic nail design the scores the 7-8 scores got the frequency of 2 or 6.25 percent with a remarks of “very good” Lastly the scores of 9-10 got the highest frequency of 30 or 93.75 percent with a remarks of “excellent” The results showed that the post-test of the grade 8 students have an “excellent” understanding in terms of the Practice basic nail design.

Table 13. *Distribution of the Respondents in Performance after Game-Based Learning*

Rating	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
Above 90	17	53.2	Excellent
85-89	13	40.6	Very Good
80-84	2	6.2	Good
75-79	-	-	Fair
Below 75	-	-	Poor
Total	32	100	

Legend: Below 75- Poor 75-79-Fair 80-84-Good 85-89-Very Good Above 90-Excellent

Table 13 shows the TLE Grade 8 students' performance after Game-Based learning . According to the categorization above there's no students got the below 75 and 75-79 rating. While the rating of 85-89 got a frequency of 2 or 6.2 percent got the remark of “Good” Meanwhile the rating of 85-89 got the frequency of 13 or 40.6 percent with the remark of “Very Good” and lastly there's a 17 frequency or 53.2 percent got the ratings of 90 with the interpretation of “Excellent

Table 14. *Significant difference between the Pre Test and Post Test score of the respondents using the Game-Based Learning.*

Game Based Learning	Pre Test		Post Test		T	Df	Sig. (2 tailed)
	Mean	Sd	Mean	Sd			
Use of Nail Care Tools and Equipment	3.93	1.998	8.90	1.399	-13.275	31	.000
Maintain Tools and Equipment.	3.37	1.385	6.43	1.966	-7.726	31	.000
Practice Occupational Health and Safety procedures	3.87	1.879	8.56	1.564	-13.775	31	.000
Practice basic nail design	8.56	1.564	9.71	.683	-4.94	31	.000

Table 14 shows the significant difference between the result of pre-test and post-test score in Beauty care (Nail care) competencies in terms of Use of nail care tools and equipment in pre test with the mean of 3.93*, standard deviation of 1.99*, while in the post got the mean of 8.90*, Standard deviation of 1.39* with the T result of -13.27*. Followed by the Maintain tools and equipment in pre test with the mean of 3.37*, standard deviation of 1.38* while in post test got the mean of 6.43* with the standard deviation of 1.96* with the T result of 7.72*.

Meanwhile the Practice of Occupational health and safety procedures in pre test got the mean of 3.87* with Standard deviation of 1.87* while in post test the Mean is 8.56* with standard deviation of 1.56 * with the T result of -13.77*. Lastly in Practice of basic nail design the pre test got the mean of 8.56* with the standard deviation of 1.56* while in post test the mean is 9.71* with the standard deviation of .683* with the T test of -4.946. The Df result of the Use of nail care tools and equipment, Maintain tools and equipment, practice occupational health and safety procedures and practice basic nail design are same with 31 result and significant 2-tailed are same with 0.000 result.

Table 15 shows the significant relationship of game-based learning in student's performance in the second quarter grade. The data show that game based learning in terms of functionality has no significant relationship as shown by the value of -0.81. It followed by Accessibility with no significant relationship with the value of -178. Lastly there is also no significant relationship of game based

learning on student's performance in terms of Technicality with the value of $-.072$.

Table 15. *Relationship Between Game based learning and Student's Performance in Second Quarter Grade*

Game-Based Learning	Student's Performance r-value
Functionality	$-.081$
Accessibility	$-.178$
Technicality	$-.072$

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

Game-Based Learning in educational strategies studies use this facility in learning especially with complex courses Blanié, Amorim, & Benhamou, (2020) Of these, education stimulus was often used as an educational strategy to improve learning outcomes (ALFarsi et al., 2020). Also, game-based learning aims to develop enthusiastic learners, motivate and engage students, reduce monotonous learning methods, and help students focus, self-esteem, and memory. Various types of educational games are applied and used in educational institutions, schools, and homes (Alfarsi & Alsinani, 2017). The use of games in education is primarily focused on improving critical thinking skills while teaching specific topics by allowing students to think outside the box while adhering to the rules. Other games can be used to limit the improvement of knowledge on a particular topic, and the most popular are math games (Frey et al., 2019; Tawafak,., & Romli, Ruzaini, and Sohail, 2019).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion were drawn: The hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the learning performance of learners before and after the Game-Based learning materials was not supported by evidence, hence it is not accepted.

The school administrator may give new opportunities and teaching strategies by using a game-based learning instruction that learner acquire the necessities for the teachers to improve their teaching competence. Teachers teaching T.L.E. subjects may consider using game-based learning as instructional tools for teaching TLE subjects for the improvement of students performance. This is so since it resulted significantly in the students gaining skills based on their perception. It will also help the teacher enhance their teaching strategies. This study also suggests other method and strategies for teaching other grade level. This may enhance the learning performance in TLE and other subjects. Future researchers may carry out these studies to keep in touch with the new teaching methods using game-based learning materials to gain and to improve learning outcomes in this subject.

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